

ISic3338

I.Sicily inscription 3338

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

ash chest

Editor

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Autopsy

2006.07.25; 2013.09.30

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Found c.1884 in Akradina, behind convent of Santa Lucia in predio Avolio (cf. n.15411 also)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 15410

Physical Description

A white marble ash chest, relief carved in the form of a temple with fluted ionic columns on the corners and a lid (11.5cm high) in the form of a tiled roof with acroteria at the corners and a shield in the centre of the pediment. The front long side has birds and garlands in relief, surrounding a moulded panel bearing the inscription. The short sides contain panels with a jug and a patera.

Dimensions

Height 39 cm

Width 48 cm

Depth 29 cm

Layout

Latin text centred over four lines in a panel in the upper middle of the long side of the chest. The letters decrease slightly in size over the four lines.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. C(ai) · Servili · C(ai) · f(ilius) · Q̄uir(ina tribu)

2. Avite · pie · salve

3. vixit · an(nos) · XVII ·

4. diebus · XI ·

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

Caius Servilius Avitus, son of Gaius, of the Quirina tribe, a dutiful man, farewell!
He lived 17 years, 11 days

Commentary

It should be noted that the report in NSA for 1884 records differing dimensions (50.7 x 42 cm) from those in the museum inventory, and reports that the urn was found without a lid; the text, identical, is said there to be reported from a squeeze.

Digital identifiers:

TM 492388

EDCS 34700076

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 163

Henzen, W., Zangemeister, K. F. W. 1872-1913. *Ephemeris epigraphica. Corporis inscriptionum Latinarum supplementum*, edita iussu Instituti archaeologici Romani. Berlin. At VIII 694

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3338. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4358217>

